

OJS Statistics and Reports for SSHRC - ASJ 2025

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Introduction

This guide was prepared by Coalition Publica to assist journals using **Open Journal Systems (OJS)** in their application to the 2025 SSHRC Aid to Scholarly Journals (ASJ) program.

Many statistics related to articles, authors and referees can be compiled using the statistics module in OJS, though their availability may depend on your journal's configuration and publishing practices. Basic readership and impact module statistics are also available, but a dedicated analytics system like Google Analytics or Matomo can be connected to OJS and may be better suited to answer some questions. Note, these tools only begin collecting data from the time of installation and cannot provide retrospective data.

The data requested in the 2025 SSHRC ASJ application are for the period of **June 1, 2023, and May 31, 2025**. The SSHRC application has two streams, the instructions below apply to the established journals stream; emerging journals can use select instructions that apply to their requirements.

Article Data Section

If you are using **OJS 3.3**, you will need to pull two reports - Articles and Views - to compile the information for this section. For **OJS 3.4+** you will need to pull the Articles report. For both versions, you can also use the Editorial Activity page.

Articles Report

- Contains metadata about all articles in the journal, including incomplete, in progress, and published submissions.
- Unfortunately, for OJS version 3.3, the Articles report does not contain the date published as a value, but this can be retrieved from the views report, see below.

Where to download:

- Journal Manager, Journal Editor, or Administrator can download the Articles report in CSV format from **Statistics > Reports > Articles Report**

Tips:

- This report can get quite large, especially for journals with a long history. Be patient as it generates. If you experience any issue or receive errors, contact your site admin.
- It contains columns for multiple authors so there may be a lot of empty cells. Scroll to the right to see further article information. You may want to delete or hide empty columns for your analysis.

- To identify and filter out incomplete submissions, use a combination of “Status” column: “Submission” and “Date submitted”: empty (no date)

View report (OJS 3.3)

- View report contains a count of abstract (article landing page) views and file (galley) downloads for each article, as well as article title and publication date.

Where to download:

- Journal Manager, Journal Editor, or Administrator can download the Articles report in CSV format from **Statistics > Reports > View Report**

Editorial Activity visualization

- The Editorial Activity page allows to see at a glance editorial statistics, such as the number of submissions received/accepted/declined/published over a given period.

Where to access:

- Journal Manager, Journal Editor, or Administrator can view the visual editorial activity under **Statistics > Editorial Activity**
- From this display, a date range can be applied to display data for a certain period.
- The data on this page is not available for download as a CSV, but the same data can be calculated from the Articles report.

Detailed instructions for ASJ requirements

For OJS 3.3, to retrieve required data and to facilitate analysis we recommend you use spreadsheet functions to add the data from the “Date Published” column from the **Views report** to your **Articles report** using the Submission ID / Article ID in the first column as the unique identifier that will be the same between the 2 reports.

**Aid to Scholarly Journals Program
General Support**

Application - Article Data (Mandatory)

Note: In this context, "article" always refers to peer-reviewed articles.

Number of issues per year

Total number of issues

Minimum number of articles per issue

Maximum number of articles per issue

Total number of articles published

Total number of articles published in a language other than French or English

Specify the languages
(255 chars)

Number of articles published in fields supported by SSHRC

	Number of articles submitted	Number of articles accepted	Number of articles published
By researchers	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
By students	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>

Average time from submission to acceptance in months

Average time from acceptance to publication in months

- Number of issues per year
 - Count **manually** on the Archives page or using the **Views report**
- Total number of issues
 - Count **manually** on the Archives page or using the **Views report**
- Minimum and maximum values of articles per issue. Includes: peer reviewed articles per SSHRC definition. Excludes: introductions; individual book, article or event reviews; letters to the editor; and editorials.
 - If these distinctions are reflected via respective journal sections, or via article keyword or subject tags, then the count can be retrieved by combining the volume information from the **Views report** with data from the **Articles report**. See respective columns for "Section title", "Keywords" etc.
 - If not, count manually based on the Archives page or using the **Views report**.
- Total number of articles published
 - This count can be retrieved from the **Articles report**. Filter published articles by "Status" column: "Published".
 - Additionally, in **OJS 3.3** this count can be retrieved from the **Views report**. All articles in the Views report are published, no additional filtering needed.
- Total number of articles published in a language other than English or French

- In the **Articles report** the “Language” column records language codes - this would require submission language to be accurately selected for respective articles.
 - To retrieve the count of published articles in the **Articles report**, filter by “Status” column: “Published”.
 - Alternatively, count manually from the Views report.
- Number of articles submitted
 - Number of articles accepted
 - Number of articles published
 - This information can be retrieved from the **Editorial Activity** visualization.
 - SSHRC requires you to distinguish between student and faculty authors. This cannot be done automatically, but if it is in your practice to ask your authors to include this data in their Bio Statements, then it can be retrieved from the Articles report, “Bio Statement” column. The collection of student status may also be facilitated by the use of ORCID iD which are also recorded in the Articles report.
- Average time from submission to acceptance (in months)
 - Calculate the average from the dates recorded in the **Articles report**:
 - Find submission date in the “Date submitted” column
 - Filter “Editor decision #” column by “accept submission”
 - For filtered results, locate acceptance date in “Date decided #” column
 - Average time from acceptance to publication (in months)
 - In **OJS 3.3** this requires combining data from **Articles report** and **Views report**
 - Calculate the average from the dates recorded in the “Date submitted” column of the **Articles report** and the “Date published” column of the **Views report**
 - In **OJS 3.4+** calculate the average from the dates recorded in the **Articles report**
 - Find submission date in the “Date submitted” column
 - Find publication date in the “First published” column

Referees section

For this section, you can use the **Review report**.

Review Report

- This report contains information on all reviews done for journals’ submissions, including reviewer details, dates, and comments

Where to download:

- Journal Manager, Journal Editor, or Administrator can download the Articles report in CSV format from Statistics > Reports > Review Report

Detailed instructions for ASJ requirement

“Attach a PDF document listing the referees most often used in the peer review process between June 1, 2023, and May 31, 2025. Indicate their institutional affiliation and the number of articles they each reviewed.”

- List of referees (most often) used in the peer review process
 - Including institutional affiliation
 - Number of articles they each reviewed

Tips for retrieving the required data from the Review report:

- Each review round is listed on its own row, so the same submission may appear in the report multiple times. Use the “Submission Title” or “Submission ID” column to identify the submission.
- The report contains the names of all reviewers contacted for each article
 - The “Declined” column indicates whether they accepted or declined the review assignment. Filter based on < Declined = no > to ensure you only include valid reviewers in your analysis
- Ensure you remove duplicate entries of reviewers for the same article over multiple review rounds
 - You can do this by sorting columns Family and Given names alphabetically first and then reviewing the Submission ID and removing duplicates manually or using spreadsheet functions

Authors section

For this section, you can use the list of authors/co-authors from the **Articles report**.

Detailed instructions for ASJ requirement

“Attach a PDF copy of the list of researchers whose work was accepted or published in the journal between June 1, 2023, and May 31, 2025. For co-authored works, include all authors. List only the author(s) for works that meet the SSHRC definition of an article. For each author, indicate their institutional affiliation and the number of articles that were published in the journal during the above-noted period.”

- List of researchers whose work was accepted or published
 - For co-authored works, include all authors.

- indicate their institutional affiliation
- the number of articles they authored

Tips for retrieving the required data from the Articles report:

- This is an article-centred rather than author-centred report, so you will need to manipulate the data from multiple columns to account for co-authorship in the total number of articles they authored.
- Use the “Status” column to include accepted and published articles. This includes the statuses: “copyediting”, “production”, “scheduled”, “published”.

Readership data and impact measures section

For this section, you can make use of some basic statistics available in OJS or use a connected analytics tool. The report you will need to pull will depend on your OJS version.

Custom report (OJS 3.3)

- Allows you to retrieve the counts of file (galley) downloads, abstract (article landing page) views, issue table of content views, and journal homepage views.
- Country data will be captured if configured.

Where to download:

- Journal Manager, Journal Editor, or Administrator can download the Articles report in CSV format from **Statistics > Reports > Generate custom report**
- See [Custom Report Generator instructions and sample reports](#) on PKP Docs Hub and below for detailed instructions on pulling required reports.

Visual usage statistics (OJS 3.4+)

- Visual statistics allow to preview, filter, and download reports containing the counts of file (galley) downloads, abstract (article landing page) views, issue table of content views, and journal homepage views.
- Country data will be captured if configured.

Where to download:

- Journal Manager, Journal Editor, or Administrator can view the visual statistics under **Statistics > Articles**
- From this display, a date range can be applied to display data for a certain period.
- “Download report” button under the graph allows you to download the data in CSV for the specified period. See detailed instructions for pulling required reports below.

Subscription report, if applicable

- Subscription report contains information on individual and institutional subscribers in the journal.

Where to download:

- Journal Manager, Journal Editor, or Administrator can download the Articles report in CSV format from **Statistics > Reports > Subscription Report**

Information from other tools

- Analytics tools, such as Google Analytics and Matomo, can provide more rich and detailed usage statistics than built-in OJS tools.
- A journal can be connected with Google Analytics and Matomo using the respective default plugins in OJS.
- Note that in order to generate usage statistics for periods in the past, Google Analytics or Matomo data collection would need to have been enabled during the reporting period.

Detailed instructions for ASJ requirement

Available in OJS:

- average number of visits per day
 - **3.3** Familiarize yourself with the general instructions in the [Custom Report Generator instructions and sample reports](#) on PKP Docs Hub
 - Select “Article abstract page views” from the dropdown box.
 - Uncheck all boxes under “Aggregate stats by.”
 - Enter a date range.
 - Under Advanced Options, select “Day” as your column
 - Generate custom report and calculate the average
 - **3.4+**
 - Select your date range
 - Make sure the view is toggled to “Abstracts” and “Daily”
 - Under Download Report select the option to Download Timeline and then calculate the average
- number of full-text article downloads per month
 - **3.3** Follow the instructions in [Example report: How well has a particular \(i.e., most recent\) issue performed over the last few months?](#)
 - Adjust date ranges and omit the instructions to narrow down by a particular issue
 - **3.4+**

- Select your date range
 - Make sure the view is toggled to “Files” and “Monthly”
 - Under Download Report select the option to Download Timeline
- average number of full-text views for the top 20 articles
 - **3.3**
 - Follow the instructions for the [*Example report: What are the most downloaded articles over the last 5 years?*](#)
 - Adjust date ranges. From the resulting spreadsheet, calculate the average from the top 20 in the list.
 - **3.4+**
 - Select your date range
 - Under Download Report select the option to Download Articles and then calculate the average from the top 20 in the list

May be available in OJS - if configured

- geographic locations of visitors
 - **3.3**
 - Follow the instructions for the [*Example report : What countries are downloading our articles \(for a specific date interval\)?*](#)
 - **3.4+**
 - Select your date range
 - Under Download Report select the option to Download the Geographic Report

Unavailable in OJS - a dedicated analytics system like Google Analytics or Matomo would be better suited to answer these questions

- number of visitors per month
- number of unique visitors per month
- percentage of new vs. returning visitors
- average visit duration
- average number of pages viewed per visit

Provide subscription statistics (e.g., paid, unpaid, individual, institutional)

- A list of individual and institutional subscribers, including the details of subscription types as defined by the journal, can be retrieved from the **Subscriptions report**

If your journal is on the Érudit platform

Érudit will provide you data files in your Editorial Dashboard. In your publications tsv file there is a column “document type”, you can filter by “article” to include only peer-reviewed articles and it also contains a column “language”. This may the following statistics easier to compile:

- Minimum and maximum values of articles per issue
- Total number of articles published
- Total number of articles published in a language other than English or French

Combining Statistics

OJS distinguishes between “abstract views” which are used to tally “visits” in this guide, and “file views” which are used to count “downloads” in this guide.

Érudit uses COUNTER compliant statistics which by this standard definition combines full text views and downloads.

You can combine the Érudit **consultation** statistics with the OJS **file view/download** statistics for the following statistics:

- number of full-text article downloads per month
- average number of full-text views for the top 20 articles
- the geographic locations of visitors, if available

We do not recommend combining Érudit **consultation** statistics with OJS **abstract views/visits**.

For further help

- If your journal is hosted at a library, they may be able to provide assistance
- You can always ask questions on the [PKP Community Forum](#)
- There is a comprehensive guide to [OJS statistics](#) on the PKP Docs Hub
- There is a [“Live” Google Doc version of this guide](#) that you can consult for updates and community questions